

Alphabetic Romanticism

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Just like how we cannot sufficiently capture the complexities of human character and social interactions within the frame of spacetime, the alphabets are not any different.

Here is a sneak peek into the world of the alphabets, where we unravel the intricate personalities and relationships beneath the Gothic strokes that give structure to our expressions. Sit down and engage your imagination for a cognitive spin ride into the universe of the alphabets.

A and **B** are “frenemies.” **A** is better looking than **B**. **A** is tall and built; he has got a nice masculine body, but **B** does not. He has a pot belly instead. **A** and **B** are in a silent contest to be **C**'s lover. **C** is beautiful and mature, but she is confused about the choice of whom to pick as her lover between **A** and **B**. **C** has a younger brother, **D**. **D** is still young and immature; he has no self-control. He does not make his sister's life any easier because she has to babysit him. **D** attends the same secondary school with **E** and **F**. **E** and **F** are the types people easily mistake as fraternal twins

when, in actual fact, they are not. **F** is older than **E** yet; they are in the same class in school. **E** is mentally agile, but **F** has some challenges academically; hence, they are in the same class. Nevertheless, they do not allow these differences to affect their friendship. **E** and **F** absolutely do not like **D**. They cannot stand seeing him along the walkways in school. One day, **E** got into a fight with **D**. As expected, **F** joined the fight, and **D** got the beating of his life.

F and **G** are friends, though **G** is older than **F**. It is the kind of friendship where one is old enough to be the other's uncle. **G** and **H** are not really close. Maybe it's because they share very few things in common. Obviously, they aren't hating on each other; I guess it's just a reality they have accepted. **I** and **J** are good buddies. They became friends after attending a musical event. After realising that they have a lot in common, their friendship was sealed. Interestingly, **J** is older than **I**.

J and **K** are people from different worlds. Their story is like that of two people who met and at first glance hated each other. But no one knows why really. **K** and **L** are bad boys—yes, very bad boys. They live very careless lives: clubbing, drinking excessively, smoking all sorts of things, using hard drugs, and chasing women as if it's their life's mission. They are true hedonists, always seeking pleasure.

K is older than **L**, and sadly, he influenced **L**. **K** and **L** have **M** and **N** as side chicks, whom they lead this careless lifestyle with. **M** and **N** are regular clubbers (not strippers), and it's obvious they are not serious about their education. They just like having fun. **M** is older than **N**, and **N** than **O**. **M** and **N** have begun influencing **O**. Compared to **M** and **N**, **O** is still young and naïve. She is oblivious to the repercussions surrounding **M** and **N**'s lifestyle. **O** comes from a very religious home; her parents are very strict. At the end of the day, **O** is influenced by **M** and **N** and even begins to beat them in their own game. To end their story, **M** and **N** turned a new leaf and became serious with their lives, but **O** never changed.

P is the kind of person you will describe as a church guy, a saint. He is not like **K** and **L**, but he did live a somewhat questionable life before taking religion seriously. He is tall, smart, and hardworking. He is not a flirt. **P** preaches to **Q** to believe in Jesus and be born again. **Q** is not a bad boy like **K** and **L**, but he is definitely a sinner, as **P** always says. **R** is a friend to **Q**. He eavesdrops whenever **P** is preaching to **Q**. He

does not give his opinions nor does he argue. **R** is acts like he does not want to believe in the gospel, but deep down in his heart, he knows he needs it. I forgot to add, **Q** is effeminate and **R** wears dreadlocks.

R and **S** are friends—just friends—although they are almost too close to be called platonic friends. **S** has a huge crush on **T**. She does not want him to know for fear of embarrassing herself. **S** is a very beautiful and attractive lady, and **T**, on the other hand, is a handsome and brilliant man—a successful, hard working entrepreneur. **T** has a feeling that **S** secretly admires him, but he does not yet want to approach her about it. **T** is definitely **S**'s dream guy. I hope they eventually take the opportunity to fan this spark of theirs into wild flames of love. They seem to be a perfect match for each other.

The relationship between **T** and **U** is like that of a mentor and a mentee. **T** is already a successful entrepreneur, but **U** is just coming up. He is on the way to becoming a star like **T**. He is giving his best to ensure his business thrives, but some things are not coming easily for him. The journey to becoming a successful entrepreneur can be difficult and frustrating at times. He is so focused on being successful that he does not even have time to think about getting into a relationship. I guess his time just hasn't come.

U and **V** are not buddies at all; they have nothing in common, although people think they look alike. Apart from **U** being older than **V** and more hardworking, **V** is still a high school student, and **U** is a university graduate. **U** considers relating with **V** to be like the forehead communicating with the shoulder, and that's just impossible. **V** and **W** are related—obviously two v's make a w. But it's not the cousin type of relationship; they are actually neighbours. **W** tells **V** some of her life's issues. Please don't be mistaken; they are not in a relationship. In fact, **W** cannot fathom it—**V** has been friend-zoned. **W** has feelings for **X**, even though they are still teenagers and have a long way to go in life. **V** follows **W** whenever she goes to visit **X**. He acts like some sort of watchdog for her, in case anything too heavy for words happens between **W** and **X**, because her parents will literally kill her if it did. "Sex thrum" or whatever it is called in their world. After all, her parents have warned her, "No man must touch you until you are married."

X is a really cool guy, and it's no wonder **W** likes him. He is really good-looking and has swag. **X** and **Y** are "bros," really good friends who watch each other's

backs. **Y** and **Z** are siblings; **Z** is older than **Y** by five years. **Z** is like those older sisters who don't like to show how deeply they care about their younger siblings until something bad happens. **Z** likes to masquerade her caring side under sarcasm. **Z** is a very beautiful and mature lady; she is an indoor person who enjoys reading novels and escaping into her own fantasy world. She constantly dreams of the day her own "Prince Charming" will come.

Welcome back, homo sapiens. Sorry if that ending was too abrupt. I hope with this brief exposé I have been able to construe that beneath our expressions

with the English alphabets are beautiful, somewhat quirky, and unbelievable personalities of sounds and letters who are able to mysteriously conceal their true identities from their users. Certainly, it's not their intention. We are probably too distracted stringing letters together enough to pay good attention. This piece might just change how we view the alphabets—from servants of our daily expressions to delicate, complex beings with identities.